

**ACADEMICS. AND BEYOND: THE IMPACT OF SAINT FRANCIS OF ASSISI
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ENGAGEMENT FROM S.Y. 2023-2024**

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Academics. And Beyond: The Impact of Saint Francis of Assisi College's Developmental Activities on Students' Social Engagement from S.Y. 2023-2024

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Abstract

This study examined the engagement of students in various developmental activities implemented by the school, focusing on affective, behavioral, and cognitive domains. The study employed quantitative approach using surveys on student engagement, followed by statistical analysis to identify correlations between students' assessments of activities and their levels of engagement. The findings revealed that students showed strong engagement across all domains: affective engagement (mean=3.32) was categorized as Strongly Agree, behavioral engagement (mean=3.06) as Agree, and cognitive engagement (mean=3.30) as Strongly Agree. Statistical analysis found significant relationships between students' assessments of activities and their engagement, with correlation coefficients ranging from 0.424 to 0.606, all exceeding the p-value threshold of 0.05. These results indicated that students' participation in developmental activities positively influenced their emotional, behavioral, and cognitive development. The study highlighted the significant role of extracurricular activities in fostering students' personal growth, emotional well-being, and academic performance. The positive correlations between engagement and participation emphasized the importance of creating a supportive and challenging school environment.

Keywords: *developmental activities, student engagement, school environment, personal growth, academic performance*

Introduction

The Philippine education system adopted the K-12 curriculum starting in the academic year 2012-2013, aiming to provide a sufficient number of years for children to master basic academic competencies and related skills. Aside from various subject areas, learners are also encouraged to go beyond learning within the classroom. According to Learning Link Academy (2023), one of the distinct advantages of private institutions over government-facilitated schools is their recognition of extracurricular activities. As per Barge (2020), extracurricular activities refer to tasks performed outside the classroom that do not contribute to a learner's grade, including sports, arts, community service, employment, hobbies, and academic activities. Meanwhile, Bartkus et al. (2012, as cited in Civitci, 2015) defined extracurricular activities as voluntary tasks that do not mandate student participation, such as club participation, sports, and arts or music-related activities. Although extracurricular activities are driven by students' interests, Fares et al. (as cited in Boy et al., 2022) stated that, though non-mandatory, these activities are often sponsored by the school faculty.

The above-mentioned literature demonstrates the implementation of extracurricular activities, which has led to the recognition of their impact on learners in various aspects. Participation in these activities generally helps learners become more academically competitive, encourages positive character and social development, and instills the value of community involvement (Christison, 2013). While extracurricular activities (ECAs) are said to contribute to improved leadership and social skills, they appear to be less significant to the academic performance of students from a state university. This conclusion stems from a study conducted by Afalla (2020), which examined both the positive and negative impacts of extracurricular activities and their relationship with students' academic performance. The study's findings were determined using descriptive and inferential questions with a randomly selected sample group. Similarly, in the study of Boy et al. (2022), which aimed to identify the influence of extracurricular activities on the compassion, academic competence, and commitment of collegiate students, data were gathered from 365 respondents using a descriptive-correlational design. The study found that participation in ECAs positively affects students' compassion and commitment but negatively impacts academic performance.

Co-curricular activities have become an essential component of the educational landscape in the Philippines, reflecting a broader global trend toward holistic education. These activities, which include science fairs, debate clubs, math competitions, school publications, language clubs, and field trips related to academic subjects, complement the academic curriculum and provide students with opportunities for personal growth, skill development, and social engagement. There has been a significant evolution in the adaptation of co-curricular activities in Philippine schools, driven by educational reforms, technological advancements, and societal needs.

The adaptation of co-curricular activities in Philippine schools has been influenced by several key factors. The implementation of the K-12 educational reform in 2012 marked a significant shift by restructuring the basic education curriculum and emphasizing holistic student development. This reform highlighted the importance of co-curricular activities in fostering essential life skills, preparing students for higher education, and equipping them with workforce competencies.

A study by Feldman and Matjasko (2005, as cited in Guo & Liem, 2023) found that participation in co-curricular activities positively correlates with academic performance. Students engaged in these activities often exhibit higher levels of motivation and a greater sense

of belonging, leading to improved attendance and grades. Co-curricular activities are instrumental in developing essential soft skills such as leadership, communication, teamwork, and problem-solving. According to Hazilah et al. (2013, as cited in Mohamad et al., 2022), co-curricular activities serve as a medium to enhance students' personalities by nurturing additional value through skill development. Mastering soft skills is essential for students to improve their employability, as a lack of these skills may limit their employment opportunities. Recent literature, including a review by Eccles and Barber (1999, as cited in Careemdeen, 2023), highlights the positive impact of co-curricular activities on students' social and emotional well-being. These activities provide a supportive environment where students can explore interests, build self-esteem, and form meaningful relationships with peers. In the Philippines, co-curricular activities have also been a platform for promoting cultural awareness and civic engagement. Bearn (2005, as cited in Abrea, 2015) emphasized that institutions prioritizing student satisfaction, persistence, and learning must offer extensive extracurricular activities that support the academic mission and institutional goals.

The adaptation of co-curricular activities in Philippine schools reflects a dynamic and responsive approach to education. These activities have evolved to meet the changing needs of students and the broader societal context, emphasizing the development of well-rounded individuals equipped with both academic knowledge and essential life skills. The importance of co-curricular activities is well-documented in recent research, highlighting their role in enhancing academic achievement, developing soft skills, promoting well-being, and fostering civic responsibility. As the educational landscape continues to evolve, co-curricular activities will remain a critical component of the school curriculum, supporting the holistic development of students and preparing them for the challenges and opportunities of the future.

In line with these previous studies, Saint Francis of Assisi College (SFAC) is committed to providing comprehensive education that goes beyond academic excellence. Recognizing the importance of holistic development, SFAC offers a wide array of developmental activities that seamlessly integrate extracurricular and co-curricular elements. This combination is designed to foster growth and development in multiple dimensions—academically, socially, and personally.

Extracurricular activities at SFAC cover a range of interests, from sports and the arts to clubs and student organizations, allowing students to explore their passions, develop new skills, and engage meaningfully outside the classroom. Meanwhile, co-curricular activities are intricately linked to the academic curriculum, providing opportunities for students to deepen their understanding of course material through practical experiences, such as workshops, seminars, and field trips.

By merging these two types of activities, SFAC creates a nurturing environment where students can cultivate essential life skills like leadership, teamwork, and effective communication. This holistic approach ensures students are not only academically prepared but also equipped with the emotional and social competencies necessary for success in the modern world. Through this comprehensive program, SFAC strives to develop well-rounded individuals capable of making meaningful contributions to society.

While other studies have focused on the impact of co-curricular and extracurricular activities, this present study specifically examines how these developmental activities affect students' social engagement. The primary objective is to assess how the activities implemented during S.Y. 2023-2024 influence students' social aspects. Therefore, the researchers believe this research will provide insights into the impact of various developmental activities at Saint Francis of Assisi College on students' social engagement, focusing on their affective, behavioral, and cognitive aspects. Thus, the study results will benefit the following groups:

To the students, the findings will provide valuable insights into how participation in various developmental activities may contribute to overall growth, including emotional well-being, active involvement, and cognitive development. By reflecting on these impacts, students can recognize the importance of engaging fully in these activities to achieve personal and academic outcomes.

To the stakeholders of various institutions, this study offers evidence-based recommendations for improving the design and implementation of developmental activities to promote student engagement in impactful programs aligned with academic goals for holistic development.

To future researchers, this study's results may serve as a reference for those conducting similar research on the impact of school activities on students.

Research Questions

Generally, this study aimed to determine the impact of developmental activities, both co-curricular and extra-curricular, on students' social engagement at Saint Francis of Assisi College. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the assessment of the students on the various developmental activities implemented by the school?
2. What is the assessment of the students' engagement in the various developmental activities implemented by the school in terms of:
 - 2.1. cognitive engagement;
 - 2.2. behavioral engagement;
 - 2.3. affective engagement?
3. Is there a significant relationship between students' assessment of the various developmental activities and their engagement with these activities?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive research design with quantitative analysis to achieve its objectives. Descriptive research aims to characterize a population and its attributes, emphasizing "what" rather than "how" or "why" something occurs (McCombes, 2019). A checklist survey was administered to gather data on the impact of developmental activities on the social engagement of junior and senior high school students at Saint Francis of Assisi College.

Respondents

To examine the impact of developmental activities on students' social engagement at Saint Francis of Assisi College, a Random Sampling Method was used. Thomas (2020) described this method as one in which each individual has an equal chance of being chosen. The researcher's used the Slovin's formula in order to determine the number of respondents that is needed in the study. The respondents were then selected randomly among the school population as this was implied in the sampling method in order to avoid bias in the conduct of the study.

Instrument

For this study, the researchers utilized an adapted questionnaire derived from two foundational sources. The first set of statements, aimed at assessing the implementation of various developmental activities, was adapted from the study of Hart et al. (2011). This source provided a framework for evaluating how well the developmental activities implemented within the institution. The second set of statements, focused on evaluating students' engagement with these developmental activities, was adapted from the work of Gentry et al. (2002). This section included items to assess students' cognitive, behavioral, and affective engagement with the activities.

All the statements adapted from these studies were modified to align with the research objectives. The research questionnaire was divided into two parts. The first part focused on students' assessment of the implemented developmental activities. The second part contained items that would assess the students' engagement with the various developmental activities in terms of cognitive engagement, behavioral engagement, and affective engagement. This dual-structured approach allowed the researchers to comprehensively examine both the quality of the developmental activities and the students' level of engagement in them. In order to secure the validity of the instrument, the researchers consulted two field experts to check the accuracy of their questionnaire.

Procedure

To achieve the research objectives, the researchers followed a structured approach for data collection. The process began with the preparation of a formal letter of request addressed to the principal for permission to conduct the study. Upon receiving approval, the researchers proceeded to notify the selected respondents—students who would be included in the study. Each student was provided with a consent form to ensure informed participation. For those who were under the legal age of consent, a similar form was sent to their parents or guardians, informing them of their child's involvement in the research study. Once the consent forms were completed and returned, the researchers distributed the research instrument to the respondents. The instruments were carefully collected after completion, and the data were assembled for analysis.

To maintain the integrity of the research process, the researchers adhered to strict confidentiality protocols in handling the responses. They ensured that no conflicts of interest arose during the study. The data collection phase took place between March and April, with the entire study completed by the end of the school year 2023-2024. The data collected were then analyzed using appropriate statistical procedures, in line with the objectives of the study.

Data Analysis

The researchers employed the following statistical tools to assess the impact of Saint Francis of Assisi College's developmental activities on the social engagement of students:

Weighted Mean was used to assess how students rated various developmental activities at the school. It also helped determine the students' engagement in these activities, focusing on cognitive, behavioral, and affective engagement.

Pearson R Correlation Coefficient was used to explore the relationship between students' assessments of the developmental activities and their level of engagement in these activities. The Pearson correlation is a measure of the linear relationship between two variables, where values close to +1 or -1 indicate a strong positive or negative relationship, respectively, and values near 0 suggest no significant relationship. The use of Pearson's correlation allowed the researchers to determine whether there was a statistically significant relationship between the students' evaluations of the developmental activities and their engagement in them.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher ensured that all research protocols involving ethics in research were complied with for the protection of all people and institutions involved in the conduct of the study.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the outcome of the quantitative analysis of the research questions and answers. The results are presented based on the sub-variables of the study.

Assessment of the Students on the Various Developmental Activities Implemented by the School

Table 1. *Interest*

Statement	\bar{x}	Interpretation
1. School developmental activities fit my interests.	3.20	Agree
2. I have an opportunity to work on school developmental activities that interest me.	3.39	Strongly Agree
3. What I do in school developmental activities gives me new ideas.	3.28	Strongly Agree
4. I learn interesting concepts from various school developmental activities.	3.30	Strongly Agree
5. The teacher encourages me in various school developmental activities.	3.35	Strongly Agree
6. Things I do on various school developmental activities are interesting.	3.27	Strongly Agree
Categorical Mean	3.30	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD) | 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree (D) | 2.50 - 3.24 Agree (A) | 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)

Table 2. *Challenge*

Statement	\bar{x}	Interpretation
1. The activities I do in my school are challenging.	3.22	Agree
2. I have to think to solve problems in school.	3.53	Strongly Agree
3. I challenge myself by trying new things.	3.21	Agree
4. My participation in school developmental activities can make a difference.	3.07	Agree
5. I find tasks in the school demanding.	2.82	Agree
6. I am challenged to do my best in school.	3.59	Strongly Agree
Categorical Mean	3.24	Agree

Legend: 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD) | 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree (D) | 2.50 - 3.24 Agree (A) | 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)

Table 3. *Choice*

Statement	\bar{x}	Interpretation
1. Things I do in school developmental activities fit my abilities.	3.26	Agree
2. The school developmental activities are difficult.	2.90	Strongly Agree
3. I can choose to work in a group when participating in school developmental activities.	3.10	Agree
4. I can choose to work alone when participating in school developmental activities.	2.97	Agree
5. When we work together, I can choose whom I will be working with in school developmental activities.	3.12	Agree
6. When there are many options, I can choose the school developmental activity that suits me.	3.45	Strongly Agree
Categorical Mean	3.13	Agree

Legend: 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD) | 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree (D) | 2.50 - 3.24 Agree (A) | 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)

Table 4. *Enjoyment*

Statement	\bar{x}	Interpretation
1. I like participating in various school developmental activities.	3.05	Agree
2. I look forward to participating in various school developmental activities.	3.11	Agree
3. I have fun participating in various school developmental activities.	3.34	Strongly Agree
4. I like what I do in various school developmental activities.	3.39	Strongly Agree
5. The school developmental activities I do in our school are enjoyable.	3.31	Strongly Agree
6. I like participating in various school developmental activities.	3.05	Agree
Categorical Mean	3.24	Agree

Legend: 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD) | 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree (D) | 2.50 - 3.24 Agree (A) | 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)

Assessment of the students' engagement in the various developmental activities implemented by the school in terms of affective, behavior, and cognitive

Table 5. *Affective*

Statement	\bar{x}	Interpretation
1. I think what we are learning in school developmental activities is interesting.	3.31	Strongly Agree
2. I enjoy learning new things by participating in school developmental activities.	3.34	Strongly Agree
3. I like the school developmental activities implemented in our school.	3.28	Strongly Agree
4. I am proud that the school has implemented various school developmental activities.	3.37	Strongly Agree
5. I am happy to be joining various school developmental activities.	3.27	Strongly Agree
6. I think what we are learning in school developmental activities is interesting.	3.31	Agree
Categorical Mean	3.32	Strongly Agree

Table 6. Behavior

Statement	\bar{x}	Interpretation
1. I try hard to do well in school developmental activities I join.	3.34	Strongly Agree
2. I work as hard as I can when I participate in school developmental activities.	3.31	Strongly Agree
3. I volunteer to help with school developmental activities.	2.90	Agree
4. I take an active role in school developmental activities.	2.85	Agree
5. I am an active participant in school developmental activities.	2.91	Agree
Categorical Mean	3.06	Agree

Legend: 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD) | 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree (D) | 2.50 - 3.24 Agree (A) | 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)

Table 7. Cognitive

Statement	\bar{x}	Interpretation
1. I try to understand the things I learn in school developmental activities.	3.48	Strongly Agree
2. I try to combine different pieces of information from various school developmental activities.	3.32	Strongly Agree
3. I make up my own examples to help me understand the important concepts from school developmental activities.	3.13	Agree
4. I figure out how the learning from various school developmental activities might be useful in the real world.	3.26	Agree
5. I try to understand the concepts from school developmental activities by relating them to things I already know.	3.35	Strongly Agree
Categorical Mean	3.30	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD) | 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree (D) | 2.50 - 3.24 Agree (A) | 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)

Significant relationship between students' assessment of the various developmental activities and their engagement with these activities

Table 8. Affective – Interest, Challenge, Choice, and Engagement

Variables	R Value	P Value	Decision	Interpretation	
Affective	Interest	0.603	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Challenge	0.424			
	Choice	0.594			
	Enjoyment	0.535			

Level of Significance: 0.05

Table 9. Behavior – Interest, Challenge, Choice, and Engagement

Variables	R Value	P Value	Decision	Interpretation	
Behavior	Interest	0.496	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Challenge	0.451			
	Choice	0.561			
	Enjoyment	0.606			

Level of Significance: 0.05

Table 10. Cognitive – Interest, Challenge, Choice, and Engagement

Variables	R Value	P Value	Decision	Interpretation	
Cognitive	Interest	0.440	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
	Challenge	0.471			
	Choice	0.437			
	Enjoyment	0.481			

Level of Significance: 0.05

The table 1 shows the students' assessments of various developmental activities they participated in, with an overall categorical mean of 3.30, interpreted as "Strongly Agree."

Five items were rated with the interpretation "Strongly Agree": "I have an opportunity to work on school developmental activities that interest me" (\bar{x} = 3.39), "The teacher encourages me in various school developmental activities" (\bar{x} = 3.35), "I have an opportunity to work on school developmental activities that interest me" (\bar{x} = 3.30), and "What I do in school developmental activities gives me new ideas" (\bar{x} = 3.27). One item was rated with the interpretation "Agree": "School developmental activities fit my interests" (\bar{x} = 3.20).

All items ranged from "Agree" to "Strongly Agree," with no items falling under "Disagree" or "Strongly Disagree." This indicates that students believe participating in various developmental activities successfully captures their interest.

Extracurricular activities, combined with co-curricular activities, contribute significantly to the overall development of students. These activities enhance mental agility, encourage participation, responsiveness, confidence, and independence. Research indicates that both extracurricular and co-curricular activities positively impact academic performance and social interactions. Engaging in extracurricular activities offers students valuable experiential learning opportunities, fostering the development of character and social skills. Beyond

improving communication and teamwork skills, students acquire both task-oriented and relationship-oriented roles. These activities enhance team cohesion and collaboration while also promoting independence and self-confidence. Well-designed and engaging extracurricular activities are instrumental in cultivating well-rounded individuals who are prepared for the industry (Mishra & Aithal, 2023).

According to Zyrdore (2024), discovering passions beyond one's academic major enriches the college experience and positively influences others. Student organizations offer skills that are often not acquired through formal education. These groups contribute to the development of teamwork abilities, enhance self-confidence, improve time management, and, importantly, provide insight into personal interests and self-awareness.

Rahman et al. (2021) also mentioned that co-curricular activities offer students the chance to apply their knowledge and skills, explore new abilities and interests, and enhance their social and organizational skills. By participating in co-curricular activities related to their field of study, students can gain practical experience and expertise.

The table 2 presents the assessment of how various developmental activities challenge students, with a categorical mean of 3.24, interpreted as "Agree." This indicates that students assess the activities as sufficiently challenging to help them acquire new skills.

Among all the statements, "I am challenged to do my best in school" has the highest mean of 3.59 and is interpreted as "Strongly Agree." This suggests that students feel challenged to exert significant effort in the activities they participated in, reflecting a positive environment. According to Jang et al. (2014), it is important for students to perform challenging tasks while also receiving autonomy support. This combination can lead to intrinsic motivation, which helps improve academic performance.

Next, the statement "I have to think to solve problems in school" has a mean of 3.53 and is interpreted as "Strongly Agree." This shows a shift toward improving critical thinking and engaging in problem-solving. According to a study by Doleck et al. (2018), integrating activities that trigger problem-solving skills is crucial in enhancing students' cognitive abilities, preparing them for the complexity of real-world challenges.

Lastly, the statement "The activities I do in my school are challenging," with a mean of 3.22, can be interpreted as "Agree," suggesting that challenging activities are crucial for students' development. These activities push students out of their comfort zones and promote resilience and perseverance. According to Dezfuli's study, challenging academic activities are essential for fostering intellectual growth. They encourage active engagement and a deeper understanding of the students' surroundings as they complete difficult tasks.

These findings collectively suggest that the challenging and problem-solving nature of school activities plays a vital role in the academic and personal development of students.

The table 3 shows the choice of students about their assessment of various developmental activities implemented by school with a weighted mean of 3.13 that can be interpreted as AGREE. This assessment of students to various developmental activities shows their choosing ability and decision making on which aspect they can be more functional in engaging themselves with various developmental activities.

Among all statements, "When there are many options, I can choose the school developmental activity that suits me." has the highest mean of 3.448 which can be interpreted as STRONGLY AGREE. It is followed by the statements, "Things I do in school developmental activities fit my abilities." with a mean of 3.256 interpreted as AGREE; "When we work together, I can choose whom I will be working with in school developmental activities." with a mean of 3.120 interpreted as AGREE; "I can choose to work in a group when participating in school developmental activities." with a mean of 3.104 interpreted as AGREE; "I can choose to work alone when participating in school developmental activities." with a mean of 2.968 interpreted as AGREE and "The school developmental activities are difficult." with a mean of 2.896 interpreted as AGREE.

Results showed that students' choice on various developmental activities plays a vital role in determining the extent of their productivity. In which they categorically employ the essence of decision making in choosing and considering factors with regards to developmental activities. According to Kisser (2020), Student choice leads to increased engagement and empowerment. It inspires students to want to learn new things. It allows students to show what they know, but to take it so much further. Student choice creates an environment where students discover what they want to learn. To support it, she also added that Student choice enhances students' excitement about topics, curriculum, and their interests. Creativity is an essential skill for our youth, and these experiences increase their imagination. They discover powerful skills and increase their interests. These types of choices allow more meaningful learning to occur. Choice of students about various developmental activities leads to engagement and discovery in which through choosing from different factors that might help them, they also discover what areas and strategies they are good with and in which environment they can suit better. Offering students choices for non-preferred tasks or tasks that they find challenging gives them more control over their own learning and fosters independence (Allen, 2024).

Based on Mizener and Williams (2018), providing students with choice has been shown to improve perceived self-competence and performance on a variety of academic tasks, including reading, mathematics, homework, and assignment completion. This aligns with the result that various developmental activities provide opportunity for students to find where they can suit and fit in. In which they can also examine the difficulty and upon knowing it, students can be more critical to choose for what is better and competent in

performing various developmental activities.

In conclusion, choice also plays a big role in students' development. Particularly, the choice brought by different activities makes student to engage themselves, examine the present factors and learn better upon making a decision on various matters with regards the developmental activities.

The table 4 shows the assessment of students regarding various developmental activities they participated in, with a categorical mean of 3.24, interpreted as "Agree."

Three items were rated with the interpretation "Strongly Agree": "I like what I do in various school developmental activities." ($\bar{x} = 3.39$), "I have fun participating in various school developmental activities." ($\bar{x} = 3.34$), "The school developmental activities I do in our school are enjoyable." ($\bar{x} = 3.31$). Two items were rated with the interpretation "Agree": "I look forward to participating in various school developmental activities." ($\bar{x} = 3.11$) and "I like participating in various school developmental activities." ($\bar{x} = 3.05$).

All items ranged from "Agree" to "Strongly Agree," with no items falling under "Disagree" or "Strongly Disagree." This indicates that students believe participating in various developmental activities brings joy to them.

According to the study of Naorem (2023), extracurricular activities can significantly positively impact subjective well-being. Such findings contribute to the better understanding of the relationship between well-being and extracurricular activities. Also, it can have implications for the stakeholders in bringing about the holistic development of students.

The article posted by St. Johnsbury Academy (2024) emphasized that through extracurricular activities, students learn the value of hard work, enjoyment, and goal-setting, laying a strong foundation for future success. Engaging in activities equip students with advanced skills that prepare them for their professional future. With these skills, they are better equipped to overcome challenges and achieve success and happiness. Additionally, Henderson (2022) indicated that whether it is sports practice, music lessons, or simply catching up with friends, children who participate in after-school activities are more likely to feel happier and healthier.

The table 5 shows the affective engagement of students in various developmental activities implemented by the school with a weighted mean of 3.32 that can be interpreted as STRONGLY AGREE. This engagement is reflected in their interest and positive emotional response in the activities, as well as the enjoyment of learning, and pride in participating.

Among all the statements, "I am proud that the school implemented various school developmental activities" has the highest mean of 3.37 which can be interpreted as STRONGLY AGREE. It is followed by the statements "I enjoy learning new things by participating in school developmental activities" with a mean of 3.344 interpreted as STRONGLY AGREE; "I think what we are learning in school developmental activities is interesting" with a mean of 3.31 interpreted as STRONGLY AGREE; "I like the school developmental activities implemented in our school" with a mean of 3.28 interpreted as STRONGLY AGREE; and, "I am happy to be joining various school developmental activities" with a mean of 3.27 interpreted as STRONGLY AGREE.

Results showed that the students' affective engagement is greatly influenced by the various developmental activities implemented by the school. According to Myers (2019), affective domain covers the sense of belonging of the students inside the school community. Based on the study, 50% of the respondents were able to display a sense of connection with the school environment through implemented school activities. Connectedness among different people acquired through various developmental activities gives them the sense of identification in the institution where they belong, as 80% of their respondents have gained positive changes in their affective domain. Based on the results of the study conducted by Fredericks, et. Al., (2016), it is crucial to foster student's sense of belonging and emotional investments in different school activities. This aligns with the results in this study where students express their pride and happiness as they get involved which led to the strengthening of their emotional connection to the school.

Another study from Roorda et al. (2017) stated that the positive relationship between the teacher and the students can also impact their affective engagement through the encouragement they have received. It likely contributes to their emotional engagement as mentioned in the results of their study.

The increased level of enjoyment, interest, and pride reflect upon the success of the institutions' efforts in fostering a supportive environment for the emotional aspect of its students through the implementation of different school activities.

The table 6 shows the behavioral engagement of the students on various developmental activities implemented by the school where it has a weighted mean of 3.06 which can be interpreted as AGREE. Behavioral engagement is reflected in student's active participation in developmental activities, their effort in tasks, and their willingness to help in school activities.

The statement with the highest mean of 3.34 and "I try hard to do well in school developmental activities I join" is interpreted as STRONGLY AGREE indicates that the students aim to succeed in the activities where they are participating. According to Fredericks et al. (2016), active participation of students in different school activities can develop their sense of responsibility and commitment. As suggested by Caremdeen (2023), inclusive and structured extracurricular programs can positively enhance the engagement and participation of the students. The statement "I work hard as I can when I participate in school developmental activities" with a mean of 3.31 interpreted as STRONGLY AGREE, indicates the substantial effort of the students. As supported by Bezerina et al. (2020), where a correlation between the effort and the improvement of the academic and the personal outcomes was found. Unlikely, the

statement “I volunteer to help with school developmental activities” has a lower mean of 2.90 and can be interpreted as AGREE, it can be seen that the student also shows willingness to contribute. According to Bartkus et al. (2012) voluntary participation can foster leadership skills and involvement in the community.

In conclusion, students’ behavioral engagement in various developmental activities reflects their efforts to excel as well as in their active participation. Its alignment with existing research showcases the effectiveness of the activities in elevating the students’ involvement and commitment. The encouragement and opportunities provided for them can cultivate a culture of engagement and dedication among the students. This approach not only promotes students’ behavioral engagement as well as prepares them for the future challenges of learning new life skills and developing a strong sense of community.

The table 7 shows the cognitive engagement of the students in various developmental activities implemented by the school with the weighted mean of 3.30 that can be interpreted as STRONGLY AGREE. This engagement is reflected by cognitive development of students in terms of having critical and analytical skills gained from various developmental activities.

Among all the statements, “I try to understand the things I learn in school developmental activities” has the highest mean of 3.48 which can be interpreted as STRONGLY AGREE. It is followed by the statements “I try to understand the concepts from school developmental activities by relating them to things I already know.” with a mean of 3.35 interpreted as STRONGLY AGREE; “I try to combine different pieces of information from various school developmental activities.” with a mean of 3.32 interpreted as STRONGLY AGREE; “I figure out how the learning from various school developmental activities might be useful in the real world.” with a mean of 3.26 interpreted as AGREE; and, “I make up my own examples to help me understand the important concepts from school developmental activities.” with a mean of 3.13 interpreted as AGREE.

Results showed that the students’ cognitive engagement is greatly influenced by various developmental activities implemented by the school. According to Millaci (2022), cognition includes the general processes of perception, attention, memory, working memory, pattern recognition, executive function, concept formation and reasoning, intelligence, and academic achievement. Additionally, just as with their physical bodies, there are specific activities and games that can help children develop cognitive skills. This aligns with the result of this study as cognitive engagement helps students to understand, learn and conceptualize concepts about the activities. In the study conducted Berezina et. al (2020) reveals that developmental activities allow a holistic approach to the development of pupils-intellectual abilities, aimed at activating mental activity, improving attention, memory, and perception. The acquired skills in sports games (basketball, floorball), as well as a conscious attitude to physical exercises contribute to the self-development and self-improvement of children. Cognitive engagement is greatly influenced by developmental activities as one of the findings talks about ideas learned from activities that can be used in real world context.

In conclusion, cognitive engagement to various developmental activities of students helps them to attain holistic growth. Aside from physical well-being as the direct effect of developmental activities, their mental capability is also challenged to be more critical and analytical to understand information and create concepts.

The table 8 shows the relationship between students’ assessment of various developmental activities and their engagement with these activities. The computed r values of 0.603, 0.424, 0.594, and 0.535, with an alpha value of 0.05, are greater than the p -value of 0.00001. Therefore, the NULL HYPOTHESIS IS REJECTED. This indicates a significant relationship between students’ assessment of the various developmental activities and their engagement with these activities in terms of affective outcomes.

Joining in various developmental activities at school has a positive impact on students’ engagement, particularly in terms of their affective aspect. According to Wilson (2019), students involved in extracurricular activities tend to experience reduced stress, anxiety, and depression, highlighting the therapeutic benefits of these activities in fostering resilience and emotional intelligence.

An article posted by Vikasconcept (2024) indicated that students who participate in extracurricular activities experience lower levels of stress, anxiety, and depression. This underscores the therapeutic benefits of such activities in promoting resilience and emotional intelligence.

Participation in co-curricular activities is associated with improved emotional well-being among students. These activities offer chances for social interaction, personal growth, and skill development, all of which positively impact emotional health. Research indicates that students who are heavily involved in co-curricular activities report higher levels of subjective well-being compared to their less involved peers. Activities such as outdoor exercise, socializing, and music have been shown to be particularly beneficial for emotional well-being. Additionally, involvement in co-curricular programs is linked to enhanced psychological well-being, including personal growth, positive relationships, and a sense of purpose. Overall, co-curricular activities are essential for promoting emotional health by fostering social connections, personal development, and overall well-being (PubGenius Inc. 2024).

Furthermore, Hossan et al. (2021) cited participation in co-curricular activities with improved subjective well-being. These activities provide opportunities for building interpersonal connections, developing personal identity, and acquiring emotional, social, academic, and career-related skills.

The table 9 shows the relationship between students’ assessment of various developmental activities and their engagement with these activities. The computed r values of 0.496, 0.451, 0.561, and 0.606, with an alpha value of 0.05, are greater than the p value of 0.00001.

Therefore, the NULL HYPOTHESIS IS REJECTED, indicating a significant relationship between students' assessment of the developmental activities and their engagement with these activities in terms of behavior.

Ahmad (2016) opined that student involvement in co-curricular activities fosters the development of social skills crucial for future success and contributes to the formation of well-rounded human capital in both academic and character aspects. Mastering social skills is essential as it enhances positive relationships for students. Active participation in extracurricular activities beyond the classroom setting enables students to engage with teachers and peers, acting as a catalyst for their social skills development. Moreover, these activities contribute to the holistic development of students, improving their physical, emotional, spiritual, and intellectual aspects.

Also, findings from the study of Zaheer (2023) revealed that most teachers believe co-curricular activities significantly boost students' confidence. Participation in these activities enhances students' social interaction, motivation, and regular school attendance. Engaging in various activities, such as sports and debates, helps students become more goal-oriented and improves their communication skills. Additionally, co-curricular activities facilitate the management of different tasks, foster leadership qualities, and promote teamwork. Through these activities, students build self-esteem, strengthen their connection to the school, and develop a sense of responsibility.

Moreover, Rani and Keshwal (2016) revealed that co-curricular activities enhance the social skills of children with intellectual disabilities. These children often experience significant limitations in intellectual functioning and adaptive behavior, which impede their typical social skill development. While they may learn at a slower pace compared to their peers, their social skills can improve significantly when they participate in suitable co-curricular activities alongside their regular academic work. Typically, cognitive development is emphasized in functional academic teaching, with less focus on affective and psychomotor aspects. Co-curricular activities address these areas by providing enjoyable experiences through which children can learn and practice social skills.

The table 10 shows the relationship between students' assessment of various developmental activities and their engagement with these activities. The computed r values of 0.440, 0.471, 0.437, and 0.481, with an alpha value of 0.05, are greater than the p -value of 0.00001. Therefore, the NULL HYPOTHESIS IS REJECTED. This indicates a significant relationship between students' assessment of the various developmental activities and their engagement with these activities in terms of cognitive aspects.

According to the study of Ayaz et al. (2017), co-curricular activities contribute to a child's mental, physical, social, moral, and emotional development. Their research focused on assessing the impact of these activities on students' academic performance at the secondary school level. Their study concluded that by participating in various school activities, students experience a significant positive effect on their academic achievement.

As emphasized in the article of Medowie Christian School (2023), engaging in activities that students enjoy can significantly boost their self-esteem and confidence. This boost in confidence can lead to a positive effect on their academic performance, making them more at ease when sharing their ideas and more resilient when facing academic challenges. Extracurricular activities not only foster character development but also provide cognitive benefits. For instance, participating in activities like music, chess, or debating can improve cognitive skills such as memory, attention, and problem-solving. These enhancements can notably benefit a student's academic achievements, especially in subjects that require strong problem-solving skills or memory recall.

Furthermore, findings from the study of Billingsley and Hurd (2019) revealed that encouraging participation in Extracurricular Activity Involvement (ECAI) could be a valuable approach to enhancing academic success by mitigating the negative psychological health effects that underrepresented students may experience due to discrimination.

Conclusions

Students' experiences with different school developmental activities are generally favorable in terms of interest, challenge, choice, and enjoyment, according to evaluations of these activities. Students agree, or strongly agree, that these activities are pleasurable to engage in, suit their interests, challenge them suitably, and present them with relevant options.

The assessment of the students' engagement in the various developmental activities implemented by the school which covers their affective, behavior and cognitive engagement. Through the findings it can be concluded. This research, overall, underscores that challenging and engaging academic environments are a high-importance part of students' cognitive and motivational growth. These findings all suggest collectively that the school, through its stimulating and challenging academic environment, achieves more than academic success; it gains personal growth for its students as well. However, in the future, what will retain this success at school is making sure that activities are challenging and supportive, creating a culture of continuous improvement and engagement for students.

These development activities have a strong influence on students' social engagement – affective, behavioral, and cognitive aspects, as evidenced by the high correlation found between students' assessment of developmental activities and their participation. The fact that the null hypothesis was rejected in each instance emphasizes how significantly these activities contribute to the general development and well-being of students. The identified favorable connections are consistent with previous research that emphasizes the advantages of extracurricular activities in terms of stress reduction, resilience building, social skill enhancement, and improved academic achievement.

Based on the results of this study, the following recommendations are suggested:

To maximize participation and rewards, schools should provide a wide variety of co-curricular and developmental activities to meet the interests and needs of different student populations.

Establish initiatives that promote engagement in social skills and confidence-building activities, as these are essential for students' academic and personal development.

To guarantee that students consistently profit from their involvement and to combine academic and personal growth chances, consider incorporating specific developmental activities into the academic curriculum.

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